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Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder and Childhood Trauma among Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Childhood trauma is recognized as a significant risk factor for the development of post-traumatic stress disorder during adolescence, a period marked by heightened emotional and psychological vulnerability. The present study aimed to examine the relationship between childhood trauma experiences and PTSD symptoms among adolescent. A sample of N=189 adolescents were recruited from Faisalabad district using purposive sampling. Data were collected using the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire-Short Form and the PTSD Symptoms Checklist for DSM-5. The result of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation revealed a significant positive association between childhood trauma (all-subcales: emotional abuse, physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional neglect, and physical neglect) and Post-traumatic stress disorder (all-subcales: re-experiencing, avoidance, negative alterations, and hyperarousal) $r = .78^{**}$. The Linear Regression Analysis indicated that post-traumatic stress disorder is the significant predictor of childhood trauma $r = .22^{**}$ among adolescents. Meanwhile, the independent sample t-test showed that female adolescents reported significantly higher childhood trauma (with all subscales) and post-traumatic stress disorder (with all subscales) as compared to male adolescents. These findings underscore the critical need for early identification, prevention, intervention programs within schools and communities to address trauma-related mental health concerns. The study highlights the importance of fostering trauma informed practices among educators, parents, mental health professionals to promote resilience and psychological wellbeing in Pakistani adolescents.

Keywords: Childhood Trauma, Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder, Ptsd, Adolescents

INTRODUCTION

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) represents a major mental health issue that commonly affects children and adolescents following exposure to traumatic experiences such as abuse, violence, or natural disasters (Bakker, 2020; Keller et al., 2017). The presence of PTSD during these critical developmental stages can have far-reaching consequences, impacting emotional and psychological stability, physical health, social interactions, and academic achievement (Tamir et al., 2025). According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5), traumatic experiences involve direct exposure, witnessing, or repeated confrontation with distressing details of events that entail actual or threatened death, serious injury, or extreme danger (APA, 2013).

Research indicates that exposure to at least one traumatic event is highly prevalent among children and adolescents worldwide. Studies have shown that 63% of children and 89.5% of adolescents in Linköping, Sweden, experienced trauma (Gustafsson et al., 2009); 60% of adolescents in the United States (Vacek & Whisman, 2021); 68.9% in Mexico (Orozco et al., 2008); 83.7% in the Gaza Strip, Palestine (El-Khodary et al., 2020); and nearly all adolescents (99.7%) in Soweto, South Africa (Closson et al., 2016).

According to the World Health Organization (2023), nearly three out of four children between the ages of 2 and 4 experience psychological aggression and/or physical punishment from their parents or caregivers, while approximately one in thirteen men and one in five women report a history of sexual abuse. Furthermore, an estimated 64% of children who have experienced any form of violence are from South Asia (Hillis et al., 2016). In Pakistan, there are no official national statistics available on the prevalence of different types of childhood trauma despite extensive literature

searches. However, a recent report from 2023 documented 2,227 cases of child sexual abuse (CSA), with 54% of victims being girls (Bari et al., 2024).

Research also suggests that the most common forms of trauma among male children in Pakistan are neglect and physical abuse, whereas sexual abuse is more frequently reported among female children (Zafar et al., 2020). According to Dye (2018), childhood trauma can have long-lasting and severe effects on an individual's psychological and emotional development. Such experiences may occur as single (acute) incidents or as repeated (chronic) exposures over time. Traumatic events can take place in a variety of settings—from larger social contexts such as schools, workplaces, or communities to the more intimate environment of the home (Zakar, 2016). Moreover, studies indicate that physical, emotional abuse, and neglect are most often perpetrated by family members, while sexual abuse tends to be committed by individuals outside the family circle (Zafar et al., 2020)

Traumatic experiences during childhood and adolescence have been shown to increase vulnerability to a range of mental health disorders (Ponnamperuma et al., 2020), including post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression (Vibhakar et al., 2019), and anxiety (Heim & Nemeroff, 2013). Such early adversities are also associated with negative physical outcomes, such as structural changes in the hippocampus (Malhi et al., 2019) and the development of psychopathology (Vacek & Whisman, 2021). Moreover, childhood trauma can lead to various harmful consequences, including a heightened risk of suicidal behavior (Borges et al., 2021), aggressive tendencies directed toward oneself or others (Bynion et al., 2018), and the onset of PTSD (Skandsen et al., 2023).

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is a psychiatric condition that arises following exposure to a traumatic or life-threatening event (Battle, 2013). These events may include natural disasters such as earthquakes (Tang et al., 2018), floods (Tauken et al., 2016), and tornadoes (Price et al., 2015); physical or sexual abuse (Ma & Li, 2014; Lee et al., 2018); serious accidents (Tierens et al., 2012); interpersonal violence or crime (Avanci et al., 2021; Bynion et al., 2018); or the death of a loved one and life-threatening illnesses such as cancer. The core symptoms of PTSD include intrusive or re-experiencing symptoms, avoidance behaviors, hyperarousal, and negative alterations in cognition and mood.

Most existing research on traumatized children and adolescents has focused on populations affected by natural disasters, violent assaults, war exposure, and bereavement. Studies indicate that approximately 11–72.8% of adolescents exposed to natural disasters may develop PTSD (Tang et al., 2018). Similarly, around 37–50% of adolescents who have experienced physical or sexual abuse meet the diagnostic criteria for PTSD (Horowitz et al., 2005). Among those exposed to war-related trauma, the prevalence of PTSD has been reported to range from 36–53% (Agbaria et al., 2021; El-Khodary et al., 2020).

These findings demonstrate that traumatic experiences are highly prevalent among children and adolescents. However, many young individuals lack adequate coping mechanisms to manage such distressing events, making them more vulnerable to developing PTSD. Despite this, the epidemiological understanding of traumatic experiences and PTSD among children and adolescents in Pakistan remains limited. Therefore, the present study was designed to examine the relationship between childhood trauma experiences and PTSD symptoms among adolescents.

Hypotheses

There would be a positive significant relationship between Post Trauma Stress Disorder and childhood trauma among adolescents.

Post trauma stress disorder would be a significant predictor of childhood trauma among adolescents.

There would be a significant gender differences in childhood trauma and PTSD among adolescents.

METHODS

Sample

Considering that matric and intermediate students were able to read and understand the English version of the questionnaires, a sample of 189 adolescents was recruited from both urban and rural area of Faisalabad district using purposive sampling. Prior to data collection, students were briefly screened for early signs of childhood trauma, and the concept of childhood trauma was clearly explained to them. Only those students who voluntarily agreed to participate were included in the study.

Instruments

Demographic sheet. The demographic sheet was obtained from respondents with their age, gender, education, siblings, family system and residence.

Short form of the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire (CTQ-SF) To assess early adverse childhood experiences, the English version of the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire–Short Form (CTQ-SF) was utilized. This 28-item retrospective self-report measure (Hagborg et al., 2022) evaluates various forms of traumatic experiences during childhood. Participants rate each statement on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from “never true” to “very often true,” reflecting how frequently they encountered each experience. The CTQ-SF covers five domains of childhood trauma: emotional abuse, physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional neglect, and physical neglect. Each subscale yields scores between 5 and 25, with higher scores representing more severe childhood maltreatment. Previous studies have validated the CTQ-SF for both clinical and non-clinical adolescent populations (Hagborg et al., 2022; Janiri et al., 2023), demonstrating strong reliability and psychometric soundness.

PTSD Symptoms Checklist for DSM-5 (PCL-5) The PTSD Checklist for DSM-5 (PCL-5; Weathers et al., 2013b) is a 20-item self-report instrument developed to measure symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder as defined by the DSM-5. Respondents rate the severity of each symptom on a 5-point scale ranging from 0 (“not at all”) to 4 (“extremely”), reflecting the extent of distress caused by each symptom. The scale assesses symptoms across the four DSM-5 diagnostic clusters: intrusive experiences (Criterion B), avoidance of trauma-related stimuli (Criterion C), negative alterations in cognition and mood (Criterion D), and changes in arousal and reactivity (Criterion E; APA, 2013). The PCL-5 has been widely used in both clinical and research settings to evaluate PTSD symptom severity, determine the reliability and validity of symptom reports, and inform clinical and research decision-making (Rust & Golombok, 2014).

Research Procedure

Data were collected by directly approaching adolescents in various education institutions. Prior to data collection, formal permission was obtained through an authority letter from the department of Psychology to ensure ethical approval for conducting research within the selected schools and colleges. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary. After obtaining institutional permission, the CTQ-SF

and PCL-5 were administered to participants. The purpose of the study was clearly explained, and informed consent was obtained from all students before they took part. Before filling out the questionnaires, the concept of childhood trauma and post-traumatic stress symptoms was briefly explained in simple language to ensure the clear understanding. Participants were assured of confidentiality and informed consent that they could withdraw at any stage without penalty. The researcher also addressed any queries raised by the participants and provided guidance where needed. Each respondent was given 10 to 15 minutes to complete the questionnaires. Participants who expressed interest in the findings were informed that the summarized results would be shared with them after the study's completion.

RESULTS

Table 1

Demographics Profile (n= 189)

Respondent's Characteristics		N	%	M (SD)
Age (Range = 14-18 Years)				16.01 (1.29)
Gender	Male	94	49.7	
	Female	95	50.3	
Education	Matric	96	50.8	
	Intermediate	93	49.2	
Siblings (1-7)				4.30 (1.18)
Family System	Nuclear	87	46.0	
	Joint	102	54.0	
Residence	Rural	114	60.3	
	Urban	75	39.7	

The sample consisted of 189 adolescents and age was between 14 to 18 years with a mean age of 16.01 Years (SD = 1.29). Regarding gender, the distribution was almost equal, with 49.7% males (n = 94) and 50.3% females (n = 95). In terms of education, 50.8% of participants were studying at the matric level (n = 96), while 49.2% were at intermediate level (n = 93). The respondents have an average of 4.30 siblings (SD = 1.18), with the number of siblings ranging from 1 to 7. Concerning the family system, 46% belonged to nuclear families (n = 87) and 54% to joint families (n = 102). Finally, in terms of residence, the majority of participants (60.3%, n = 114) lived in rural areas, whereas 39.7% (n = 75) resided in urban areas.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis

Variables	M	SD	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. Childhood Trauma	93.78	23.95	.91**	.91**	.91**	.93**	.84**	.78**	.38**	.31**	.36**	.36**
2. Emotional Abuse	16.84	4.49	-	.80**	.76**	.85**	.79**	.47**	.44**	.36**	.33**	.305**
3. Physical Abuse	17.46	5.21		-	.79**	.81**	.69**	.48**	.33**	.33**	.41**	.35**
4. Sexual Abuse	16.97	5.48			-	.82**	.68**	.36**	.27**	.16*	.31**	.33**
5. Emotional	16.89	4.36				-	.78**	.42**	.34**	.26**	.32**	.33**

Neglect								
6.Physical Neglect	15.26	3.99	-	.43**	.37**	.31**	.27**	.35**
7.PTSD	37.30	13.73		-	.71**	.72**	.76**	.81**
8.Re-experiencing	12.70	3.92			-	.70**	.25**	.32**
9. Avoidance	13.04	4.30				-	.24**	.31**
10.Negative Alterations	5.67	4.92					-	.69**
11 Hyper Arousal	5.89	5.09						-

** p < .01; * p < .05

The results of Table 2 show the analysis of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, which revealed a significant as well as positive relationship between childhood trauma (subscales: emotional abuse, physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional neglect, and physical neglect) and PTSD (subscales: re-experiencing, avoidance, negative alterations, and hyperarousal). This indicates that higher level of any type of childhood trauma is associated with greater PTSD symptoms among adolescents.

Table 3
Simple Linear Regression Analysis for predicting Childhood Trauma among Adolescents

	B	SE	β	T	p	CI	
Constant	12.09	3.58		3.37	.000***	5.02	19.16
Post traumatic Stress Disorder	.27	.04	.47	-7.26	.000***	.20	0.34
R ²	.22**						
ΔR^2	.21						
F	52.68						

** p < .01; CI for Confidence

The results of Table 3 showed that the overall model with one predictor (childhood trauma) explained the 22.0% (R² = .22) of variance with F 52.68, p < .01 for PTSD among adolescents. Whereas childhood trauma found to be a significant positive predictor (B = .27; β = .47; p < .01) of PTSD among adolescents.

Table 4
Gender differences (N=189)

Variable	Male (n = 94)		Female (n = 95)		t(187)	p	95%CI	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
Childhood Trauma	84.76	26.6	102.72	16.74	-5.54	.001**	-24.34	-11.57
Emotional Abuse	15.29	4.85	18.38	3.49	-5.03	.001**	-4.30	-1.88
Physical Abuse	15.68	5.54	19.21	4.20	-4.93	.001**	-4.94	-2.12
Sexual Abuse	15.00	6.09	18.92	3.93	-5.25	.001**	-5.39	-2.44
Emotional Neglect	15.33	4.76	18.44	3.28	-5.23	.001**	-4.28	-1.94
Physical Neglect	14.13	4.24	16.39	3.39	-4.05	.001**	-3.36	-1.16
PTSD	33.83	14.1	40.74	12.45	-3.56	.001**	-10.73	-3.08

Re-experiencing	12.03	4.49	13.37	3.14	-2.37	.02**	-2.45	-.22
Avoidance	12.21	4.94	13.85	3.39	-2.66	.01**	-2.85	-.42
Negative Alterations	4.46	4.27	6.87	5.23	-3.47	.001**	-3.79	-1.04
Hyper Arousal	5.13	4.85	6.64	5.23	-2.06	.04*	-2.96	-.06

The results in Table 4.5 indicate a significant gender difference in the mean scores of childhood trauma (subscales; emotional abuse, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and emotional neglect, physical neglect) and PTSD (subscales; re-experiencing, avoidance, negative alternations, and hyper arousal). Whereas the mean score of childhood trauma (subscales; emotional abuse, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and emotional neglect, physical neglect) and PTSD (subscales; re-experiencing, avoidance, negative alternations, and hyper arousal) were significantly higher among female adolescents than male adolescents.

DISCUSSION

Childhood trauma is recognized as a major public health concern that poses serious risks to both mental and physical well-being. Adolescents exposed to traumatic experiences during childhood are more vulnerable to developing a range of psychological difficulties, including depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and substance-related problems (Kolaitis, 2017). Findings from the present study supported Hypothesis 1, indicating a significant positive relationship between childhood trauma and PTSD among adolescents. These results are consistent with previous research showing that early traumatic experiences can have long-lasting negative effects on cognitive functioning, emotional stability, and overall health, often manifesting as cognitive impairments, emotion dysregulation, or mental health disorders such as substance abuse and depression (McKay et al., 2021; Strathearn et al., 2020). Moreover, earlier studies have identified childhood trauma as a key risk factor for suicidal behavior (Zatti et al., 2017) and highlighted its strong link with comorbid PTSD in later life (Dell'Aquila & Berle, 2023).

Results related to Hypothesis 2 further revealed that childhood trauma significantly predicts PTSD symptoms in adolescents. Prior evidence suggests that adolescents with a history of traumatic experiences often struggle with emotion regulation and exhibit higher levels of anxiety, depression, and PTSD symptoms (Adams et al., 2018). They may also experience alexithymia, or difficulty identifying and expressing emotions (Muzi & Pace, 2023). Trauma is believed to interfere with the normal development of the brain systems responsible for emotional control, thereby hindering adolescents' ability to recognize, understand, and manage their feelings effectively. Consequently, exposure to early life trauma has been shown to heighten vulnerability to emotional and psychiatric disorders, including PTSD (Clements-Nolle & Waddington, 2019; Wang et al., 2020).

Previous research provides strong support for the present study's findings, indicating that early life trauma is a well-established risk factor for the development of PTSD, as demonstrated in both retrospective and longitudinal investigations (Carliner et al., 2016; Moustafa et al., 2024). While a single traumatic incident may be sufficient to trigger PTSD in some individuals, repeated or multiple traumatic experiences significantly increase the likelihood of its onset (Dell'Aquila & Berle, 2023; Kolassa et al., 2010). This risk is particularly heightened among individuals exposed to chronic interpersonal traumas such as sexual abuse, caregiver maltreatment, or bullying, as well as among those who have endured diverse forms of trauma across different life contexts (Blanco et al., 2013; Dell'Aquila & Berle, 2023; Fetzner et al.,

2011).

Gender differences also play an important role in the development and manifestation of psychological outcomes following trauma. Research indicates that men and women differ in their susceptibility to psychiatric conditions and in various clinical outcomes throughout the lifespan (Baldwin & Srivastava, 2015). Consistent with this understanding, the findings of Hypothesis 3 in the current study revealed that female adolescents scored significantly higher than males on both childhood trauma (emotional, physical, and sexual abuse, as well as emotional and physical neglect) and PTSD symptoms (re-experiencing, avoidance, negative alterations, and hyperarousal). Empirical evidence supports these gender-based disparities. Previous studies have shown that female adolescents report higher rates of childhood trauma and adverse experiences compared to males (Pruessner et al., 2019; Sweeney et al., 2015). Moreover, there is widespread agreement that women are more frequently victims of childhood sexual abuse than men (Tolin & Foa, 2006). Among individuals with psychosis, research further indicates that females tend to have greater exposure to sexual and physical abuse compared to males (Fisher et al., 2009; Morgan & Fisher, 2007; Kelly et al., 2016).

Previous research has consistently shown that women exhibit a higher lifetime prevalence of PTSD compared to men (Kimerling et al., 2018). Data from the United Kingdom also indicate that women tend to screen positive for PTSD across nearly all age groups, with the exception of those aged 55–64 years (Lonnen & Paskell, 2024). Scholars suggest that this gender disparity may be attributed to a combination of pre-traumatic, peri-traumatic, and post-traumatic factors that are more commonly observed in females, contributing to greater vulnerability and symptom severity (Christiansen & Hansen, 2015). Additionally, several studies have reported that women are not only more likely to develop PTSD but also tend to experience higher levels of distress across specific PTSD symptoms and clusters compared to men (Hourani et al., 2015; Tekin et al., 2016).

The results of this study highlight the significant role of childhood trauma in the development of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) among Pakistani adolescents, offering several meaningful implications for parents, teachers, psychologists, educational institutions, and policymakers. For Parents, the findings emphasize the importance of creating a nurturing and emotionally secure home environment. Open communication, emotional warmth, and responsiveness to children's need can serve as protective factors against the long-term effects of trauma. Parents should be educated on recognizing early signs of distress, providing consistent emotional support, and seeking timely professional help when needed. While, academic institutions, the integration of trauma-informed practices and mental health awareness programs can play a crucial preventive role. Schools can establish safe and supportive environments where students feel heard and understood. Teachers, who interact with adolescents on a daily basis, are in a unique position to notice behavioral or emotional changes that may signal trauma-related difficulties. With appropriate training, they can refer students for psychological assessment and support at an early stage.

For psychologists and mental health professionals, the findings underscore the need for early identification and intervention among adolescents who have experienced trauma. Evidence-based therapeutic approaches such as trauma-focused cognitive-behavioral therapy (TF-CBT) and mindfulness-based interventions can help adolescents' process traumatic experiences, regulate emotions, and reduce PTSD symptoms. Collaboration with schools and families is essential to ensure a consistent support system.

At the policy level, there is a pressing need to integrate trauma awareness and mental health services into existing child and adolescents' health programs in Pakistan. Policymakers should promote community-based mental health initiatives, school counseling programs, and public education campaigns to reduce stigma and improve access to psychological care. Addressing both the psychological and social determinants of PTSD can significantly contribute to the overall wellbeing and resilience of Pakistani adolescents affected by childhood trauma.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study show that adolescents who experienced childhood trauma such as emotional, physical, or sexual abuse, and emotional or physical neglect are more likely to develop symptoms of PTSD. In simple terms, the more trauma an adolescent faces in childhood, the greater their chances of having PTSD related problems later on, such as flashbacks, emotional numbness, avoidance, or feeling constantly on edge. The results also revealed that female adolescents reported higher levels of both childhood trauma and PTSD symptoms compared to males' adolescents, suggesting that girls may be more emotionally affected by early aversive experiences. Overall study highlights how early traumatic experiences can have a lasting impact on mental health during adolescents.

However, this research has some limitations. The sample size was taken from only one district (Faisalabad) and included a limited number of students from matric and intermediate classes, which means the findings cannot generalize to all Pakistani adolescents. The study also relied on self-report questionnaires, which might have influenced the accuracy of responses due to underreporting or misunderstanding of questions. Future research should include a larger and more diverse sample from different regions and consider using multiple assessment methods (e.g., interviews or teacher reports) to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between childhood trauma and PTSD among adolescents.

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